

INTERNATIONAL REFUGEE LAW PSDA

by

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The International Convention in context to the Syrian Refugee Crisis:

Introduction:

The Syrian Arab Republic is one of the countries in the world. The country has been on the epitome of the modern-day warfare which has been one of the most responsive and repulsive in terms of being the house of the crisis since the 70s. The constant civil war and the responsibility which pertains to and creates the understanding that there are lesser circumstances which can justify for the needs of the war. With the latest war in action since 2015, it is one of the ghastliest wars that has been taking place in the middle east since the invasion of Iraq by the United States which caused thousands of deaths and permanently damaging the structure of Iraq and the people living in it since then. The Syrian Republic Government has been in direct conflict with the ISIS, the NATO – sponsored rebel groups who want to dethrone the Assad Government over the period of time. The war has been ongoing and from time to time there have been several countries who are directly responsible for the killings of the citizens of Syria, which includes the Government of SAR itself as well as the allies who take cognizance of the fact that there are who are directly sponsoring or indirectly conjuring the ongoing warfare which can last for a very long time.

History of the Migratory crisis:

Over the period of time, there have been certain circumstances which have prevailed over time that has been the biggest impromptu factor for the people who wish to ensure that there are no such circumstances that hold and prevail over the society and the circumstances under which that prevails, the migration crisis. Over the period of time, there have been several battles and wars

that have been taking place and providing for the best way possible to deteriorate the situation which exists in the countries who have been directly catering to the needs and wants of the people who wish to separate or clear themselves out of the various tarnishes, skirmishes and the tyrant actions. War has been responsible for dislocating millions and millions of individuals over the period of time and that, has been the biggest factor which is responsible for the newly established political game which intends to harm and create such circumstances. What one needs to realize is the fact that there are lesser circumstances that prevail over the land in comparison to the helplessness that arise from the skirmishes through the watershed bodies that hold the basic power to run any human being and society.

The ongoing Syrian warfare:

The original challenge that came into the contingency of the warfare was the establishment of the Syrian Government which was being ruled for over four decades by the Assad Family. The warfare began with the uprising against the Assad family, however it extended over the period of time towards the establishment of the Islamic State which wanted to create an Islamic state ruled by the idea of Caliphate in the countries Syria and Iraq. The complication of the warfare further increased with the coming in of the Orthodox Sunni who were directly going against the idea of accepting a Shia Muslim leader who is an ethnic minority in the country. In furtherance, the Kurdish forces that have been existing in Northern Syria, were attacked by the Turkish Government in Allegiance with NATO which goes on to prove the fact the underlying interests the NATO alliance held against the Assad Government. The Assad Regime is assisted by the Russian Government led by Vladimir Putin who has given military aide as well as the presence of the Russian Army on the Syrian soil. More than the battle by the people, Syria has become the battleground for the countries to try and test their ability to be able to fight and hold the modern-day game of warfare to retain its potential strength and capability which is inclined towards the money-minded armaments producers and the crony capitalistic friends of the Politicians of the west.

Sufferings of the Syrian Citizens:

The Syrian citizens have been influenced greatly in terms of providing for a structure wherein there have been higher amount of damages that have been unhindered but have caused several deaths which has become uncountable. The residents of Damascus, Damaa, Idlib and Aleppo have been bombed, day and night which called for deaths of over six hundred thousand and over millions have gone missing which led to such a blunder in over two decades in modern-day times. The displacement of over five million Syrians who had to rush and leave their country as they were not in the position to provide for a structured and sustainable living while they stayed inside the country. The skirmishes observed in the Syrian territory made it impossible for the folks to stay the in the North western districts of the country and thus led to the migration of the Syrian citizens to other countries.

Migration Crisis:

With the constant flood and other disruption to basic food and amenities, there has been a drastic rise in the crisis for basic needs amongst the Syrian citizen that led to the establishment of a need wherein they got to move to other countries. As it is said, over 130 countries have accepted the Syrian refugees in their respective country with certain countries such as Egypt, Iran, Turkey, Lebanon and Jordan. The highest number of Refugees that have been accepted by the Turkish Government which amounted to 3.5 million citizens whom are being taken care of. However, the migration crisis is not remaining to as such wherein the Turkish Government is being taken care of and likewise there have been several other institutions.

The International Convention on Refugee, 1951:

The international refugee convention was one of the firsts in the world that were directly involved in preserving and giving refugee and migrants a status which will be providing the best solution to anyone who has been involved in the warfare and other such circumstances that are responsible for the destruction of lands which will be protected by the ones responsible for causing such skirmishes. The International refugee convention was given the status for global acceptance in 1967 from the Euro-centric approach which made it clearer for the ones to provide

support to the refugees who have been tarnished and provided with the several battlefields. The support for the Syrian refugees.

The Hypocrisy of Europe:

The European Union was one of the first promulgators who established the ideal situation that prevailed over the territory that ensured full support to the Syrian refugees in 2015 wherein they provided for a method by which the Syrian migrants could live with the basic fundamental strengths and clauses with basic rights and other amenities being ensured. However, over the period of time, there have been several circumstances that give out the understanding which pertains to providing with the basic amenities over the period of time. With the coming in of the 2017, there was a sudden rise of the racial abuse and the Xenophobic abuse that was increasingly moving towards the idea of creating such attitudes towards the Syrian refugees. The country such as Poland, Hungary and Slovakia had created such circumstances wherein the citizens were racially abusing the Syrians as well as asking them to return back their country of origin as they were “dirtying their country”. The biggest example of Racism is calling out the Non-European Muslims as the Islamic invaders who intended to occupy and take over the society and create and Islamic Empire.¹

Conclusion:

The rise of such situation in the European Union when it comes to the acceptance and the hypocrisy it shows in the developing stage goes on to prove that there have been several circumstances which have resulted in the dichotomy in terms of action by several countries in the European Union. With the calm and reproachable attitude in terms of providing for the Ukrainians and the outright hate which is being provided goes on to show that there is nothing more of a reasoning which includes the hyperbolic activity which therefore refers to the understanding of these countrymen who try to prove that there are lesser circumstances which give out the actions of the outright Islamophobia which they hold against the Suffering Arabs

¹ Victor Orban to Germany, DW News 08th Jan 2018

and zero recognition of the facts that play an important role in the development of these citizens and helping them reprimand form the sufferings they have been circumvented to without even plying for such effortless terrorizing actions. One of the greatest example that can be pertained to is the idea of establishing the Xenophobic approach which can be observed over the period of time and has been given an impactful consideration when it comes to the needs and providing for a structured belief and must be countered in terms of providing a valid reasoning and ways with which such actions can be resolved and reduced down to normal situations in the state and the society.

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